

Assessing the Readiness Index of the Private Sector to Effectively use 5G Technology in the Urban and Peri-urban areas of Kenya.

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Abstract

Telcos in Kenya wish to leapfrog and launch 5G even though the LTE-A coverage in the country is patchy. The private sector makes up the largest consumers of telecommunication services. This paper seeks to develop a readiness index that will determine if it is business worthy for the telcos to deploy 5G services within the urban and peri-urban areas of Kenya. The readiness index will be developed based on selected factors such as infrastructure and technology available, demand for 5G services, and the country profile in terms of coverage of telecommunication services. The paper will use certain criterion metrics to assign weights to these selected factors. These weights will be aggregated to define a concrete readiness index. The paper will extrapolate the available LTE-A from the incumbent telcos in the country as well as 5G datasets from other telcos in the African continent and Europe. The readiness index will provide the necessary recommendations to the telcos to make recommendations on the suitable measures to take to ensure a smooth transition to 5G services for the telcos and their mobile users.

1 Introduction

Mobile banking has revolutionized the finance industry by enabling financial services to run on telecommunication networks. In Kenya, MPESA is the leading mobile banking platform that runs on mobile phones to serve both the banked and unbanked population [1] [2]. Having observed the tremendous impact mobile banking services have had on the economy, financial institutions are making efforts to offer their services online through mobile apps and internet solutions. This paradigm shift implies that customers must access the internet to get services through mobile applications or online banking solutions. Moreover, more essential services are being offered through online portals while, on the other hand, more people continue shopping online through various eCommerce sites [3]. Similarly, other payment platforms such as Pesapal and Jam-popay which enable e-commerce applications to have upgraded their systems to link to financial institutions to improve their service delivery. With the increasing wireless data traffic, there is need for telcos to deploy advanced technologies such as 5G to meet the demand while ensuring that the private sector data users can provide good services to their customers.

Inevitably, those who opt to use more advanced systems to improve their network performance do so at a huge cost [4] [5]. It is, therefore, paramount to find a solution that will enhance the quality of service for internet provision to meet this huge demand. The launch of 5G services in urban and peri-urban Kenya is set to meet this demand [6] [7]. The 5G technology is a dense heterogenous technology that seeks to provide for higher bandwidth to accommodate more wireless data traffic, reduce latency to improve the communication time response, and the data speeds [8] [9] by using advanced telecommunication infrastructure and a higher radio frequency spectrum band to accommodate the increased traffic. Further, 5G services are brought closer to the data users using femtocells infrastructure in enterprise buildings, or attocells infrastructure within smaller offices and residential apartments.

The paper will discuss the current state of mobile financial services, online service portals, and eCommerce platforms. Further, it will investigate the readiness index of private sector service providers to effectively use 5G technology once it is launched [10] [11]. The readiness index will seek to determine if the private sector anticipated demand for 5G services, how well the telcos are prepared for the deployment of the technology,

and how the private sector will seamlessly adopt the 5G services, and the contribution of the telcos in making the transition swift and affordable for its customer base. The paper will evaluate a set of factors to evaluate the launch of 5G services in the urban and peri-urban areas. The data filtered from LTE-A and 5G data will be analysed for these factors and weights will be allocated and aggregated using the correlation analysis model. The correlation coefficient obtained from relating these random variables will define the readiness index. The threshold of the readiness index will be set at 0.75 such that any values below the threshold will imply that the paper provides recommendations on how to improve the score, otherwise, the launch will be considered business worthy. Further, qualitative research will be conducted by carrying out scenario analysis. The data used to conduct the scenario analysis will be obtained from surveys, interviews, and review of previously available recordings. The results will inform the readiness index of the launch of 5G services in urban and peri-urban Kenya for the incumbent telcos.

2 Literature review

There has been an exponential increase in the devices connected to the internet and according to the Cisco annual internet report of 2018 [12], the number of devices is set to increase. This implies an increase in wireless data traffic which requires advanced technology such as 5G technology. Further, in Kenya, the government has been moving its services to several online platforms with the major one being Huduma Kenya [13] [14]. The private sector, with a key focus on financial and payment institutions, has been developing financial innovations to provide financial services through mobile applications and web applications. For instance, most banking institutions in Kenya run an internet platform and mobile application to allow their clients to access financial services. Some online portals developed to provide government services, require payment to be made and, as a result of this, the payment platforms rely heavily on the current type of technology available. Of these online portals, some are eCommerce sites, such as Jumia Kenya limited, that are gaining a reputation as more Kenyans prefer to shop online [15]. One of the distinct problems most companies face when making decisions on business processes re-engineering to adopt new technologies is how to ensure that the grade of service is still high. The paradigm shift to online platforms for service delivery ensures that clients can access services at any time and in their convenient location as opposed to queuing at banks or shopping malls or government offices to get services [8]. This literature review the 5G technology and services, the cost of deployment of the technology, and the merits the private sectors are set to gain. Further, this section will discuss the gap and the research methodology to determine the readiness index of the private sector in adopting 5G services.

The deployment of 5G technology in urban and peri-urban areas will improve connectivity, data rates, and reduce the latency of networks during operations. According to Yousaf, et al., 5G technology seeks to create network technologies that are in close range to the users unlike the previous technologies: 1G, 2G, 3G, and 4G [16] [17]. This is because the network aims at improving network capacity as opposed to improving network coverage [18] [8] [19]. In addition to this, the technology focusses on data traffic from indoor and outdoor communications. Safaricom Kenya is set to launch 5G in the Nairobi metropolitan which comprises the urban and peri-urban areas, in its pilot phase. The technology will conventionally use the frequency bands from the previously deployed WiMAX technology which did not gain a reputation [8]. WiMAX technology and Wi-Fi technologies were launched circa 1998 and the Wi-Fi technology gained fame over WiMAX. Safaricom is set to use the spectrum allocation set aside for WiMAX, which can be termed as a failed technology in Kenya, to launch the 5G technology. The deployment of 5G using enterprise-wide indoor antennas and wall mount outdoor antennas is set to meet the huge wireless data traffic demand by providing a wider bandwidth to accommodate more traffic. This technology is set to improve the data rates from hundreds of Mbps to tens of Gbps. This technology goes further to curb the issue of laxity in response of mobile application systems by effecting reduced latency.

An improvement in the underlying technology will provide a platform for more innovations and change in business processes for many businesses in the private sector. As earlier stated, 5G technology is deployed

to improve access by providing higher bandwidth and improve service delivery by providing higher data speeds and reduced latency of data communication [16] [20]. According to Odhiambo, et al., [13] businesses measure their service delivery in terms of the number of clients that were able to access the service and the quality of service delivery on all their platforms [1] [2] [3]. The author further describes the congestion issues that the Huduma Kenya faces when delivering services especially at the end of the month when most people need to pay bills or file their tax returns [13]. According to a working paper by the Bureau of communication and arts research on the impact of 5G on the economic growth of a country, the investment in 5G provides a platform for more innovations and developments [20] [17]. This study focuses on the productivity effects on the health sector and the substantial amounts of money a health care facility will save by deploying digital health access platforms. The aim of the innovations would be to transfer health information through mobile applications saving travel time and consultation service costs [14] [16]. In a nutshell, 5G technology lays the foundation for more innovations in the private sector with regards to improved productivity and service delivery as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The 5G infrastructure (source: Qorvo, 2017)

An assessment of the cost of deployment of the technology in the urban and peri-urban areas and the cost of investing in the technology from the end user’s perspective is crucial in determining the adoption of the technology. Despite the merits presented by launching the 5G technology in terms of improved bandwidth, data rates, and reduced latency, 5G infrastructure constraints pose a great challenge. The internet service providers or telecommunication companies providing the 5G services need to have significant amounts of upfront investment. The cost of deployment factors in the upgrades needed on the base stations, backhaul capacity, and the core networks [18] [10] [16]. A study conducted for the UK National Infrastructure Commission found that the deployment would account for 42 billion Euros in capital expenditure for the urban centers and up to double the amount to cover the rural areas [16]. Further, these firms incur an additional annual charge for purchasing spectrum bands from their national telecommunication regulators which is obtained through an auction or beauty contest [18] [16].

The cost of 5G technology deployment is set to be higher as higher quality equipment are deployed, 5G covers a shorter range hence more equipment is needed. According to BCAR study on 5G economic impact on productivity, each generation of technology advancement needs more investment to enable more services than the previous ones [17] [11]. The amount of money needed to launch the technology is a lot and on the end user side, there is need to purchase 5G enabled devices to access the 5G services from the service

providers. This research paper seeks to determine what is the cost of switching to 5G enabled devices for the Kenyan businesses and mobile users and to determine if the users switch to 5G devices how swift will the switching be or will they opt for a lock in situation.

This research work will be reviewing data obtained from reputable telcos' repositories that have already launched the technology and the impact it has had on the service delivery and improvement of innovations. Further, to determine the readiness index, the research work will determine ways in which the telcos deploying 5G services can provide incentives for the private business sector to adopt the 5G technologies as well as come up with recommendations on how to get the mobile users to adopt the technology citing how expensive infrastructure is at the onset of a launch.

3 Methodology

This research paper seeks to develop a readiness index to determine whether launching 5G in urban and peri-urban Kenya is business worthy using the methodology as illustrated in Figure 2. The initial step in this research is to determine which factors to focus on in the analysis. Firstly, the factor selection process narrows down the factors based on what interests the private sector namely: infrastructure and technology availability, demand for 5G services with the increased wireless data traffic being onboarded on the system, and the country's profile in terms of telecommunication network coverage. These factors are described further using the criterion metrics as shown in Table 1. These metrics are based on the data obtained from reputable repositories to obtain a weight metric.

Figure 2: The proposed methodology using correlation analysis and regression analysis models

The data used in this analysis is obtained from incumbent telcos within the country namely Safaricom PLC and Jamii Telecom limited. The data presents many variables and only a few factors based on the criterion metric list are chosen and filtered from the data set available. The data analysis will be done using Jupyter Notebook from Anaconda, Python for Data Science tool, which is a renown data analysis tool using the Python scripting language.

Secondly, the data is analyzed, with a key focus on the criterion metrics as the random variables to determine trends in the data. The data analysis will be done using Jupyter Notebook from Anaconda which is a renown data analysis tool using the Python scripting language. In this case, the LTE-A data obtained

from these two telcos is extrapolated to simulate a 5G scenario and the data is analyzed against the two technologies, LTE-A and 5G. The regression analysis is used to determine trends in the data with respect to the factors being estimated. The regression coefficient from the predictive analysis of these random variables is used as a weight value. All the factors are analyzed and recorded as shown in Table 1 on a metric scale of 0-100 or preferably as a fraction in the range 0 to 1.

Thirdly, the weights are aggregated using the correlation analysis. The correlation analysis model compares trends or any relationship between the random variables. The correlation is estimated in a fraction in the range of 0-1. The weight aggregates are then run through a scenario analysis. The scenario analysis uses qualitative data from surveys, interviews, and previously recorded information to determine how the variables affect each other in the market. The scenario analysis seeks to determine if there are other external factors in the industry or in the market that will affect the correlation analysis model and its operation in determining the readiness index. The scenario analysis is also scaled and given a weight.

Finally, the readiness index is obtained as an average of all the random variables' aggregated weights. The readiness index has a threshold set at 0.75. In case, the results obtained record a readiness index below 0.75, the paper will make the necessary recommendations based on the factors selected to the telcos on how they can ensure a seamless transition from LTE-A to 5G services for their customer base in the private sector. Supposing the value obtained is greater than the threshold, the launch of 5G services is considered business-worthy and the paper will make recommendations on ways to make the launch more effective based on experiences from Europe and South Africa.

Table 1: Criterion list based on the factor selection for the readiness index

Criterion	Metric Index (0-100)
LTE-A coverage level	0.5α
Fiber optic cable coverage	0.9β
Internet bandwidth per user	$0.3(\alpha+\beta)$
5G spectrum auctions	one-off $\equiv 0.5$
Effectiveness of policy makers in telecommunications	qualitative
Availability of constant electricity	nighttime light data
5G pilot	$0.5\alpha+0.7\beta$
R&D expenditure	ROI
Internet Users	5 million users
Mobile data traffic	consumption (Mbps/user/annum)

where $\alpha=[0, 100)$, $\beta = [0, 100)$, and ROI \rightarrow Return on Investment.

4 Results

The paper seeks to develop a readiness index that defines the private sector readiness to accept the 5G services in urban and peri-urban areas of Kenya. The readiness index will define the current environment providing more information on the current status of the telco market while anticipating the future market. The readiness index will guide the telco to determine if it is business worthy to invest in the 5G technology at the moment or if they should meet some of the requirements as this paper will recommend such as partnering with telephone manufacturing companies to make 5G enabled phones available as well as other networking equipment such as access points. The telcos and other investors in the telecommunication industry will use this research work to determine if, *ceteris paribus*, an investment is worthy or not.

The paper will present the findings using graphical representation of the factors selected for analysis and provide data visualizations at every level of analysis.

5 Conclusion

The assessment of the readiness index of the private sector to effectively use 5G technology in the urban and peri-urban areas of Kenya will be beneficial to the telcos as they will determine with a level of confidence if it is business worthy to launch the technology at a given time or if they have to wait until they meet certain conditions. In this paper, the readiness index was defined by analyzing the selected factors which were further defined as criterion metrics. The regression analysis model was used to determine the weights of each criterion and the correlation analysis model was used to determine the aggregated weight considering the variables under analysis are quite random.

Further, some qualitative analysis was carried out to relate the computed aggregated weight to the scenario analysis based on data collected from interviews, surveys, and reports. The result of the average of the aggregation of the qualitative and quantitative data resulted in the readiness index. The readiness index threshold used in this paper is 0.75. From the results, readiness index lower than the threshold led to several recommendations that will impact positively on the readiness for the launch of 5G services in urban and peri-urban Kenya.

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